

DOES TECHNOLOGY-BASED BANKING SERVICES POSITIVELY INFLUENCE CUSTOMERS' ADOPTION AND USAGE?

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ABSTRACT:

Currently all banking sectors in India are in the process of building world-class Information Technology infrastructure. When banks spend heavily on technology, they must ensure the facilities they offer match with the requirements of the customers. Without considering the requirements of the customers, whatever investment banks make on technology will end in the loss of both money and customer base. The customer would get empowered due to a varied choice of services available on the net at competitive cost. For the bankers, Technological banking provides more opportunity to customized services and appropriate supply and demand than the traditional services. Further, there have been many studies which have been done on technological banking services and customer satisfaction. But no comprehensive research has been made on the awareness and adoption of technological services provided to the customers and identified the problems while using technological banking services. Therefore, this study is significance to bridge this gap. So, the current study will offer many suggestions to bankers in accepting the customer preferences towards technological banking and help the banks to provide better services to the customers.

Key words: *Information technology, Adoption, Satisfaction Customers, Banks*

INTRODUCTION:

The term "Banking Technology" refers to the usage of refined information and communication technologies composed together with computer science to permit banks to offer improved services to its customers in a reliable, safe, secure and affordable way to sustain competitive benefit over other banks. Today while 'technology' refers to the information, banks use technology as an innovative means and communication technologies, computer of delivering services to customers by designing knowledge, risk quantification, innovative delivery channels and payment systems. Entry of banks gives rise to paradigm move in the ways of banking in India. The growing competition directed to improved awareness between banks on their role and significance of technology services in banking.

Technological banking services have improved the forms of three major works implemented by banks, i.e., transformation of assets, monitoring of risks and access to liquidity. From theoretical side, Banking Technology is not a stand-alone and single discipline, but there are numerous dissimilar fields such as finance (including risk management), computer science, marketing science, information technology and communication technology. Technological development will bring foremost shift in the working of banks. It would not only help them bring improvements in their internal functioning but also enable them to provide better customer service. The blast of technology is moving the banking institutions from branch banks and paper to networked banking and digitized services. It has now improved the

management systems and internal accounting of banks.

Technology will break all restrictions and encourage cross border banking business. Banks would undertake a wide-range of Business Process Re- Engineering and challenges like: -

- a) How best to provide products and services to customers?
- b) Planning a suitable organizational model to completely capture the advantages of technology
- c) How to exploit technology for creating cost efficiencies and developing economies of scale, and
- d) How to form a customer - centric operation model.

Technology is no longer being used simply as a means for automating processes. Instead, it is being used as an innovative means of distributing services to customers. The implementation of technology has directed to the following advantages: greater profitability, productivity, and efficiency; customer satisfaction and faster service; flexibility and convenience; space and cost savings; 24x7 operations. In the traditional banking system, a person had to go to a bank branch to deposit or take out money and acquire a bank statement book physically updated by a teller over the counter. With the use of computer networks, a networked printing machine in progress replaced the physical bring up to date of statements. Then ATMs were founded to facilitate deposits, withdrawals and even transfers accepting flexibility in much extensive geographical areas. Phone banking was an innovative idea in banking, and it made banking available from everywhere if mobile phones were accessible. With the effective diffusion of mobile phones, phone banking is moving into a next phase of development. Yet, one of the important modifications in banking technology is the introduction of online banking. Electronic fund transfer (RTGS/NEFT/IMPS) helps to transfer funds even on off –times. Cash Deposit Machine helps the customers for easy deposit of money in their bank accounts by avoiding over crowds in the banks.

Statement of the Problem

The wild moving globalization, competitive environment, regulation, economic changes, privatization, and the similar demands make the banks to run effectively and efficiently by updating and adopting to new technological advancements. Emergence of new products, technologies, markets, and other competitor's places demand on any institute to apply any skills that is essential to persist competitive and achieve competitive advantages. Demonetization forces the banks to implement new technological banking services. The communication technologies and information are revolutionizing the banking sector over the years. Advancement in the technology and concomitant developments in communication channels has led to in innovation of alternate delivery channels. These have improved the way in to interface the customers. There are numerous means of substitute technological banking services i.e., ATM, Core banking Solution (CBS), POS Terminals, Internet Banking, Mobile Banking, Debit Cards, Credit Cards, RTGS, EFT, MICR clearing etc. The purpose of this research is to study the customer awareness, adoption, and their satisfaction level in using the technological banking services. This study is conducted in selective Public Sector Banks and Private Sector banks in Tirupur. The respondents of the study were the customers of the banks using various technological banking services delivered by the banks. Therefore, this research attempts to examine the customer preference and satisfaction towards technological banking services.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE:

Shastri R (2001)¹ in his research entitled “Technology for Banks in India Challenges” examined the effect and challenges of new-fangled technology for banks in India. According to the research, technology has taken a sea variation in the running of the Indian banks. The previous manual structure of making of vouchers and slips was very slow. New technology being automatic is saving a lot of time, which helps in improved show of the banking industry. **Ciciretti Et Al. (2009)**² in their study “Do Internet Activities Add Value? Evidence from the Traditional Banks”, tried to deliver suggestion and implications for usage of new online technology and advanced banking products as they are related to the performance of the banks. Using diverse descriptions for what is considered as Online activity and by scrutinizing substitute proxies for bank return and threat, result showed a major link between assistances of online banking products and bank performance. Even though this link is considerably helpful for bank profits but there was a negative, slightly substantial, association among the adoption of online actions and bank risk. **Sawant BS (2011)**³ in the research paper Technological developments in Indian banking sector has observed that the banking sector supports economic growth by the introduction of information technology. The Electronic Clearance Services (ECS) formed in late 1990s, Electronic Fund Transfer (EFT) existing in mid-2000, and RTGS offered in 2004, and NEFT presented in 2005-06 with an exact goal to shape efficiency of business banks. Approximately 90 percentage of the banks have presented core banking system by the completion of 2010. The journalist have discovered about SWIFT, Bank net and NPCI and demat cards and determined that the habit of technology has stood helpful in providing services to customers.

Abu Noman Sohel Rana (2013)⁴ in his thesis, Technological Execution and Internet Banking have improved customer service and fulfillment but reduced prices in the banking industry of Bangladesh have discussed a wide issue concerning technology focused banking. In addition, it is concentrated whether technology focused banking have improved customer service, fulfillment, and reduced prices. The research has estimated the circumstances of online-based banking in Bangladesh and what customers presently think about it. An enormous number of respondents believed that technology focused banking will be extra effective and efficient for the banks and its customers. The study is made to estimate whether technological inventions and execution has improved customer service, fulfillment, and reduced prices in the banking industry of Bangladesh. The banking industry of Bangladesh is gradually accepting the newer innovation and technologies. **Rebeena Alavudeen and Dr. Sr. Rosa K. D. (2015)**⁵ in their research paper “Impact of Technological Advancements in The Banking Sector” felt that the evolution of technology has revolutionized many sectors, one of which is banking business. Banks occupy the maximum authoritative status in the current world. Strong banking organization is an essential for strong and prosperous economy. Budding banking sector is one of the causes for India's evolution. Now the innovative technology authorized banking industry to persist in the atmosphere of globalization and aggressive competition. The improvement in Information Technology has altered the working of banks and has added to its development. As a result, an extraordinary turning point has happened in the ground of modern banking. The efficient usage of technology has facilitated exact and appropriate management of the improved transaction volumes of banks, which comes with larger customer base. By designing and offering simple, safe, and secure technology, banks reach at the doorways of the customers with an independent delight of customer satisfaction. In fact, Information

technology has succeeded in creating a win-win position for all concerned segments in India. **Safeena RA, Date H (2015)**⁶ in her study "Customer perspectives on e-business value - Case Study on Internet Banking" explained the important determinants of online banking adoption are the usefulness of the system, the ease at which the online banking is done, customer awareness and knowledge about the possible risk. The online banking system is adopted due to its positive effect on the customers. Most of the online customers are aware of the risk involved in online banking.

Karthikeyan P (2016)⁷ in his study on "Technology Adoption and Customer Satisfaction in Banking Technological Services" - The determination of the research is to compare the banks founded on their adoption or practice of technology in banking services and to recognize and investigate the factors inducing the customer's adoption or use of technology in banking services. This study explores features that affect the adoption or intent to accept three e-banking technologies and fluctuations in these elements over time. This study put forward a new method to investigate adoption of new technologies and tests this method by looking into the determinants of internet banking adoption. The service industry in the world is changing, thus new technology has altered the method of customer provide services in many service organizations. Banks discover that they must continuously invent and update to preserve their demanding and perceptive customers and to provide suitable, consistent, reliable, and expedient services. **Abhishek Singh and Ashok Kumar (2017)**⁸ in their article "Technological Developments in the Indian Banking Industry" - The delayed Flaw he entitled the technological growths in the banking sector in industrialized nations have been looked to build efficiency. The article drawings the way of technological improvement in the Indian banking industry post-monetary progression (1991-1992) and identifies opening conditions as far as violent condition and managerial weights that have added to the spreading of these improvements. Banking can give valuable data about the dispersion of innovative advance as banks use technology seriously. The article talks about the consequence of open area bank unions in challenging the usage of technology and scrutinizes the suggestions of their resistance on key indicators of Public Sector Bank (PSB) efficiency. The exact analysis reveals the leading execution of the previous adopters of technology (private banks and public banks) as measured by profitability, yields on value and section of the pie, when compared with the late or unused adopters (public sector banks). Center banking recommends a move from branch banking to bank banking (outside change). IT use in Indian banking has made some amazing progress since the days when banks were seen just as instruments of social change. PSBs have still to make a considerable measure of progress as for use of technology in all their branches. **Dr. K. Mala (2017)**⁹ conducted a study under the title "An impact of technology in banking sector in India": Technology and banking are inseparable now in India. The revolution from block and mortar banking to technology driven banks has been quick during the last two eras. Technology is one of the utmost important factors for the development of mankind. The main purposes of the expansion banks are to encourage industrial growth and to develop backward areas. Banking is developing rapidly with the practice of technology in the ATM, mobile banking, online banking, etc. Plastic card is a banking invention deliver for the requirements of the retail sector has seen its numbers grow in symmetrical progression in current years. This progress has been powerfully influenced by developments in technology, deprived of which this would have been possible, of course it will change our way of life in the upcoming years. **Nakul Parameswar, Swati and Sanjav Dhir (2017)**¹⁰ conducted a study on "Banking on Innovation, Innovation in Banking at ICICI Bank" - Based in Mumbai, Industrial Credit and Investment Corporation of India Bank has

become a front-runner in its industry by intentionally using technology to widen its range to underserved consumers in rural groups with new products, financial literacy outreach, and capable modes of product delivery. Positioning itself as both technologically perception and customer-friendly, Industrial Credit and Investment Corporation of India Bank has waited ahead of the struggle by anticipating customer requirements for secure, efficient, and seamless service. But even as technology is significantly improving banking services and operations, managers still face constraints in identifying customers, keeping up to date on ever-changing strategies and motivated for endless integration through time zones all over the place. Advances in technology, the common use of the Internet, and collective frustration with traditional banking amenities and credit services have led to significant inventions in the banking sector.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study is undertaken with the following objectives:

1. To find out the customer adoption over technological services provided by the banks.
2. To analyze the purpose of using Technological banking services and to understand the customer satisfaction on the same.

METHODOLOGY

The research design of the study is descriptive in nature. The descriptive study in fact- finding examination with acceptable explanation and which are concerned with telling the features of a specific individual, or a group. In the current investigation, the sample is drawn from the customers of banking industry (public and private sector banks). The sample includes of the respondents who are easily reachable to the researcher and who meet the sampling conditions of the study. 420 respondents were totally taken for the study and each bank has different number of respondents who are selected proportionally for the study using Judgmental and Convenient Sampling method. 420 questionnaires were issued to the respondents out of which 250 were issued to public sector banks and 170 were issue to private sector banks. Hence, 420 respondents were considered for the study. The researcher has examined the completed questionnaires. The information for each item on the questionnaire has been processed and reported through a descriptive narrative. These have been accomplished by use of frequencies. Tabula presentation of the data has been made.

RESULTS AND ANALYSIS

Socio–Economic Profile and Bank Details of the Respondents

Socio – Economic profile of the respondents plays an important role for the research purpose. The socio – economic profile and bank details of the study includes Gender, Age, Educational Qualification, Marital Status, Occupation, Monthly Income, and Branch/Location of the Bank, Type of Bank and Type of the Account of Bank Customers. The following table 4.1 describes the socio – economic profile and bank details of the respondents who have been included in the study.

Socio-Economic Profile and Bank details of the Respondent

Factors	Particulars	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	281	67
	Female	139	33
Age	Less than 20 Years	104	24.8
	21 – 40 Years	261	62.3
	41 – 60 Years	48	11.5
	Above 60 Years	7	1.5
Education	School	36	8.5
	Graduate	198	47.3
	Postgraduate	168	40.0
	Others	18	4.3
Marital status	Married	181	43.3
	Unmarried	239	56.8
Profession/ Occupation	Salaried	181	43
	Business	127	30
	Retired	30	7
	Others	82	20
Monthly Income	Less than Rs.10, 000	131	31.3
	Rs.10, 001 – Rs.30, 000	192	45.8
	Rs.30, 001 – Rs. 50,000	73	17.3
	Rs.50, 001 and above	24	5.8
Branch / Location of the Bank	Urban	188	44.8
	Semi-Urban	206	49
	Rural	26	6.3
Type of the Bank	Public Sector	250	59
	Private Sector	170	41
Type of Account	Savings Account	388	92.5
	Current Account	32	7.5

Source: Primary data

From most of the respondents are male (67%), followed by female (33%). The respondents were mostly in the age group of 21-40 years (62.3%). It also states that from most of the respondents are graduates (47.3%), followed by post-graduates (40%). Out of the total respondents 56.8% are unmarried and 43.3% are married. The respondents were a mix of salaried (43%), business (30%), retired (7%) and others (20%). The table further indicated that majority of the respondents were earning between Rs. 10001 – Rs. 30000 (45.8%). Around 31.3% of the respondents had a monthly income of less than Rs. 10000, while 17.3% of the respondents earning between Rs.30001 – Rs. 50000 and around 5.8% of the respondents had a monthly income of more than Rs. 50000. The semi-urban area has the highest number of respondents (49%) out of the total sample responded followed by 44.8% from urban area and 6.3% of respondents from rural location. The respondents were predominantly customers of Public Sector banks (60%) and Private sector banks (40%). Out of 400 total respondents, majority of them were holding Savings bank account (92.5%), followed by Current account (7.5%).

SOURCE OF INFORMATION ON TECHNOLOGICAL BANKING SERVICES

Source of Information on Technological Banking Services

Sources	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Advertisement	71	17
Bank employees	166	39.5
Brochures & Booklets	29	7
Friends & Relatives	80	19
Training & Demo	29	6.8
Bank website	45	10.8

Source: Primary data

It is understood from the above table that 39.5% of the respondents used the help of bank employees, 19% of the respondents are sourced by friends and relatives, 17% of the respondent's used advertisement, 10.8% of the respondents used bank website, whereas 7% of the respondent's used brochures & booklets and 6.8% of the respondents used training & demo as a Source of Information on Technological Banking Services.

Z-TEST ANALYSIS BASED ON TWO-SAMPLE MEANS

Gender Influence on the Constructs

H0: There is no significant difference between the male and female on their level of adoption in technological banking services, Purpose of using technological services such as ATM's, Credit/Debit Card, Online Banking and Mobile Banking, Satisfaction level on using technological services on the construct.

H1: There is significant difference between the male and female on their level of adoption in technological banking services, Purpose of using technological services such as ATM's, Credit/Debit Card, Online Banking and Mobile Banking, Satisfaction level on using technological services on the construct.

Z test- Classification based on Gender

Constructs	Gender	Mean	Zo	Significance	Remark
Level of adoption	Male	30.2164	.272	.786	Not significant
	Female	30.0985			
Usage of ATM's	Male	16.5373	.360	.719	Not significant
	Female	16.6212			
Usage of Credit/Debit Card	Male	23.7649	.001	1.000	Not significant
	Female	23.7652			
Usage of Online Banking	Male	18.8657	.592	.554	Not significant
	Female	19.0455			
Usage of Mobile Banking	Male	19.5075	1.318	.188	Not significant
	Female	19.8864			
Satisfaction level on using technological services	Male	29.1157	1.074	.283	Not significant
	Female	28.8258			

Source: Primary data

From the above table, the difference in opinion between male and female is compared with constructs like level of adoption in technological banking services, Purpose of using technological services such as ATM's, Credit/Debit Card, Online Banking and Mobile Banking, Satisfaction level on using technological services, The level of significance calculated are greater than 0.05. Hence the Null hypothesis is accepted. It is concluded that the opinion between male and female are not significant.

Monthly income influence on the constructs

H₀: Respondents belonging to different monthly income groups have on an average same level of opinion on the level of adoption in technological banking services, Purpose of using technological services such as ATM's, Credit/Debit Card, Online Banking and Mobile Banking, Satisfaction level on using technological services on the construct.

H₁: Respondents belonging to different monthly income Purpose of using technological services such as ATM's, Credit/Debit Card, Online Banking and Mobile Banking, Satisfaction level on using technological services on the construct.

ANOVA- Classification based on Monthly income

Constructs	Monthly income	Mean	F	Significance	Remark
Level of adoption	Less than Rs.10,000	30.00	1.696	.167	Not significant
	Rs.10, 001 – Rs.30, 000	29.9235			
	Rs.30, 001 – Rs.50,000	31.1739			
	Rs.50, 001 and above	30.1304			
Usage of ATM's	Less than Rs.10,000	16.6480	.636	.592	Not Significant
	Rs.10, 001 – Rs.30, 000	16.4863			
	Rs.30, 001 – Rs.50,000	16.7681			
	Rs.50, 001 and above	16.1304			
Usage of Credit/Debit Card	Less than Rs.10,000	23.4560	.825	.481	Not significant
	Rs.10, 001 – Rs.30, 000	23.7377			
	Rs.30, 001 – Rs.50,000	24.3768			
	Rs.50, 001 and above	23.8261			
Usage of Online Banking	Less than Rs.10,000	18.6800	1.071	.361	Not significant
	Rs.10, 001 – Rs.30, 000	18.9399			
	Rs.30, 001 – Rs.50,000	19.4203			
	Rs.50, 001 and above	18.6522			
Usage of Mobile Banking	Less than Rs.10,000	19.7280	1.285	.279	Not significant
	Rs.10, 001 – Rs.30, 000	19.3770			
	Rs.30, 001 – Rs.50,000	19.9275			
	Rs.50, 001 and above	20.2609			
Satisfaction level on using technological services	Less than Rs.10,000	29.4080	1.681	.171	Not significant
	Rs.10, 001 – Rs.30, 000	28.7486			
	Rs.30, 001 – Rs.50,000	29.0435			
	Rs.50, 001 and above	29.0000			

Source: Primary data

From the above table it is understood that for the constructs - level of adoption in technological banking services, Purpose of using technological services such as ATM's, Credit/Debit Card, Online Banking and Mobile Banking, Satisfaction level on using technological services, the table significance values are greater than 0.05. This implies that the opinion given on the constructs by the respondents belonging to different monthly income groups do not differ significantly.

Branch/Location of the bank influence on the constructs Post Hoc Test

To find out which group differs significantly from other post hoc test is applied.

Post Hoc table comparison based on Branch/Location of the bank

Construct	Branch/Location of the bank	Branch/Location of the bank	Mean Difference	Significance	Remark
Satisfaction level on using technological services	Semi-Urban	Urban	1.185	.024	Significant

Source: Primary data

Post hoc analysis implies the mean difference between different Branch/Location of the bank. From the table 0.00 the comparison between the mean differences indicates that in the case of Satisfaction level on using technological services the respondents who are from Semi-Urban location has more Satisfaction level on using technological services than the respondents from Urban location. Thus, it is concluded that different Branch/Location of the bank of the respondents has an influence in Satisfaction level on using technological services under the study.

Major Findings:

- Out of the total respondents considered for the study, 67% of the respondents are Male and 33 % are Female respondents.
- Majority of the respondents i.e., 62.3% belong to the age group between 21 – 40 Years.
- While considering the educational qualification of the respondents, 47.3% are graduates and, 40% are postgraduates.
- The marital status of the respondents, 57% were unmarried and 43% were married.
- Considering the profession of the respondents, 43% were salaried and, 30% were business peoples.
- While analyzing the monthly income of the respondents it was found that majority of the respondents i.e., 45.8% have a monthly income between Rs.10, 001 – Rs.30, 000.
- While considering the bank location of the respondents, 49% of banks are from semi-urban area and, 44% were from urban areas.
- Predominately 59% of the respondents were selected from Public Sector bank and 41% from Private Sector Bank.
- Out of the total respondents 92.5% were savings bank account holders while 7.5% of the

respondents were holding current bank accounts.

- On construct Level of adoption in technological banking services male and female respondents do not differ significantly, but both male and female have an average same level of adoption.
- There is no significant relationship between level of adoption in technological banking services and Personal factors such as Age, Educational Qualification, Profession and Monthly income but they have a same level of adoption on technological banking services.
- There is no significant difference between the Satisfaction level on using technological services and Personal factors such as Age, Educational Qualification and Monthly income.
- On the construct Satisfaction level on using technological services and Personal factors – Profession of the respondents differ significantly.
- There is no significant difference between the Satisfaction level on using technological services and the location of bank.

CONCLUSION

The Indian banking sector had terrific improvements since nationalization in the depths of economic growth of the nation. Based on this study, the opinion of the sample respondents among the bank customers the various aspects of technological banking services provided by public and private sector banks are evaluated using appropriate statistical techniques such as Simple percentage analysis, Z test (two sample means), ANOVA (one way), Post hoc analysis. It is concluded from the results of the study that the customers are aware of technological banking services, and they have a good level of adoption in technological services. The banking customers feel that the bank must improve their quality of services and should provide user free technological services. Technology is a key factor in the banking industry which creates new business models and processes, new products and services and new delivery channels. It is essential for banks to improve strategies not only to retain its customers, but also to efficiently reduce its service charges by providing more cost-effective self-service alternatives. It is determined that “Banking without technology is not possible”. Technological banking services enables banks to get used to changes, increase productivity and efficiency, offer convenient services to customers and a special emphasis must be given for the security which would promote customers, thereby contributing to the overall growth and improvement of the country.

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